

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF HOMEROOM GUIDANCE PROGRAM IN THE DIVISION OF ISABELA: INPUT FOR PROGRAM SUSTAINABILITY AND ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the extent of implementation of the Revitalized Homeroom Guidance Program (RHGP) in the Division of Isabela, focusing on its sustainability and enhancement. The RHGP, instituted by the Department of Education, seeks to address critical student issues and support holistic development through five key domains: academic, personal, social, career, and mental development. Utilizing a descriptive research design with both quantitative and qualitative approaches, data were gathered from 317 respondents and 15 focus group participants composed of school heads, homeroom guidance teachers/designates, and parents. The findings revealed that the RHGP was generally rated as fully implemented, particularly in terms of delivery and supervision. However, administrative aspects—such as insufficient budget and lack of dedicated facilities—were partially implemented and identified as serious concerns. Statistical analysis showed a significant inverse relationship between effective program implementation and encountered challenges. It was also found that those who attended seminars or had non-core subject loads were more effective in RHGP delivery. Stakeholders uniformly assessed the program, indicating strong consensus and alignment. The study concluded that while the RHGP is functionally in place, targeted improvements in administrative support, training, resource allocation, and parental involvement are necessary for sustained implementation. Recommendations include increased funding, enhanced training, reduced teaching loads, and integration of RHGP into school improvement plans. The study emphasizes the importance of stakeholder collaboration and professional development to ensure the RHGP fulfills its role in the holistic growth of Filipino learners.

Keywords: *Homeroom Guidance Program, Holistic Student Development, Program Implementation, Educational Guidance, DepEd Isabela*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education introduced the Revitalized Homeroom Guidance Program (RHGP) to foster students' holistic development and prepare them for their societal roles. It addresses pressing concerns such as poor academic performance, bullying, risky behaviors, teenage pregnancies, online gaming addiction, and poor career decisions. In the first legislative district of Isabela, homeroom time has evolved into a space for teachers to build relationships with students and offer guidance. However, challenges such as limited instructional materials and inadequate community involvement have hindered its effectiveness. Meetings with regional officials, advisers, and counseling specialists confirmed the increasing need for a well-designed curriculum focused on academic, personal, social, career, and mental development. Community support, along with collaboration among families, schools, and local stakeholders, is essential to ensure learners' holistic growth.

In adapting to the "new normal," the RHGP aims to develop students' life skills across five domains. ASCA (2019) highlights that academic development supports learners' mastery of skills through evaluation, independent learning, and application to real-life situations. The personal and social development domain fosters self-growth through reflection, localized materials, emotional and interpersonal skills, and family engagement. Teachers facilitate teamwork, communication, and social adaptability.

Career development is addressed through career path awareness, skills training, and planning for future opportunities. Mental development includes emotional well-being, stress management, and access to counseling services.

Draayer (1961) emphasized that education must maximize learners' competencies and satisfaction. Although RHGP has been implemented, misused homeroom time and weak monitoring persist. This study investigates RHGP implementation in Isabela as a basis for sustaining and enhancing the program.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program in the Division of Isabela, an input for program sustainability and enhancement.

Specifically, the research answered the following sub-questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teachers and school heads with regard to:
 - a. Highest Educational Attainment;
 - b. Teaching/work load;
 - c. Seminar/Training Attended on Homeroom Guidance;
 - d. Position; and
 - e. Length of service as Teacher/HG?

2. What is the extent of implementation of homeroom guidance as assessed by the respondents (teachers, school heads, and parents) along:
 - a. Curriculum Implementation and Compliance;
 - b. Delivery Process;
 - c. Assessment of Learners' Development;
 - d. Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation; and
 - e. Administrative Concerns?
3. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the school heads, Homeroom Guidance Program teachers/designates, and parents on the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Division of Isabela?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondent's profile and their assessment of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Division of Isabela?
5. What are the challenges encountered by the designated Homeroom Guidance Counselor (Teachers), School Heads, and Parents in the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Division of Isabela in terms of:
 - a. Curriculum Implementation and compliance;
 - b. Delivery Process;
 - c. Assessment of Learners' Development;
 - d. Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation; and
 - e. Administrative Concerns?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' assessment of the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program and the challenges encountered?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive design which aimed at arriving at the accurate and systematic description of a population, situation or the existing phenomenon. This method as defined by McCombes (2023) is designed to answer the what, where, when and how questions, but not the why questions based on the reason that the design can use a wide variety of research methods to investigate one or more variables. In this manner, the descriptive research design illustrates the present characteristics, conditions, images, and the like based on impressions, perceptions or reactions of the respondents to a given situation. In the context of this present study, the descriptive method was used to describe the assessment of the Homeroom Guidance teachers or HG designate and school heads on the extent of implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program at the Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela.

Furthermore, the research used the quantitative and qualitative method. The quantitative method was used to obtain the data gathered as a result of the administered survey questionnaire. The qualitative part of the research was also employed to validate further the reliability of the answers of the respondents in the administered survey questionnaire, the researcher used structured interview. In obtaining the data needed as a result of interview among the participants, the study used the thematic approach in

categorizing the multiple answers of the participants. Hence, he devised sub-themes to classify the diverse responses of the participants and eventually came up with a general theme as regards the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program.

Locale of the Study

The setting of the study was specifically situated at the Legislative District 1 of Isabela from which out of the six (6) Legislative Districts of the Division of Isabela, the study considered the northern part municipalities of the province with central and non-central schools.

The study is concentrated in the one hundred thirty-one (131) elementary public schools. It has 8 districts covering the 6 municipalities which include Cabagan with 2 newly divided districts, Delfin Albano compose of 1 district, San Pablo with lone district, Sta Maria with only 1 district, Sto. Tomas same with 1 district, and the big municipality of Tumauni where the SDO-Isabela satellite office is located with 2 districts.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Elementary Homeroom Guidance teachers/designates, school heads, and parents from the eight (8) school districts that are geographically located under the Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela.

Moreover, Slovin's formula was employed to determine the three hundred seventeen (317) teacher-respondents out of one thousand five hundred nineteen (1519) total population. In detail, the respondents per district were selected through stratified proportional random sampling, composed of three hundred seventeen (317) Elementary Homeroom Guidance teachers/designates, one hundred thirty-one (131) school heads, and one hundred thirty-one (131) parents, a total of five hundred seventy-nine (579) as illustrated in the table below.

Table 1
Distribution of the Respondents According to Schools District

Schools District	Elementary HG Counselor /Teacher		School Head	Parents
	Total Population	Sample Size	Total Population	Total Population
Cabagan East District	345	45	16	16
Cabagan West District	131	34	12	12
Delfin Albano District	175	38	21	21
San Pablo District	158	39	15	15
Sta. Maria District	156	39	15	15
Sto. Tomas District	159	39	18	18
Tumauni North District	194	41	15	15
Tumauni South District	201	42	19	19
Total	1,519	317	131	131

For the qualitative part of the study, the researcher selected fifteen (15) participants and subjected them to structured interview. The identified participants who participated in the structured interview were five (5) School Heads, seven (7) Elementary Homeroom Guidance teachers/designates, and two (2) parents.

Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering the needed data, the researcher sought permission through a request letter for approval to conduct the study from the Schools Division Superintendent thru Channels. After approval, the researcher administered the survey questionnaire to the respondents either through phone calls or face to face method observing IATF Protocols for those areas with low risk of Covid 19 Status.

The respondents were given enough time to answer the survey questionnaire. After the questionnaire has been retrieved, the researcher collated and tabulated the gathered data for analysis.

Statistical Treatment of Data

As regards the statistical treatment and data analysis procedure employed in the research, data were gathered and analyzed using the following statistical tools:

1. Frequency and Percentage

This descriptive statistical tool on Frequency and Percentage was utilized to determine the demographic profile of the respondents as regards their highest educational attainment, teaching load or workload, seminar/training attended on Homeroom Guidance, teaching position, and length of service as a teacher or school head.

2. Weighted Mean

This tool was utilized to describe the extent of implementation of the homeroom guidance program (HGP), and determine the degree of seriousness of the challenges encountered by the designated Homeroom Guidance Counselor or Teachers as regards the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela.

3. One-way Analysis of Variance

This inferential statistical tool was used to test the significant difference in the assessment of the school heads, HRGP teachers/designates, and parents on the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program of the Legislative District 1 in the Division of Isabela.

4. Chi-square test

This inferential statistical tool was used to test the significant relationship between the respondent's profile and their assessment of the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program of the Legislative District 1 in the Division of Isabela.

5. Pearson product-moment correlation

This inferential statistical tool was used to test the significant relationship between the respondents' assessment of the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program and the challenges encountered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

What is the demographic profile of the respondents with regard to highest educational attainment, teaching load or workload, seminar/training attended on Homeroom Guidance, position, and length of service as a teacher or school head? Highest Educational Attainment of the Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates and School Heads

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents
in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Homeroom Guidance Teacher/Designate		School Head	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree	105	33.12	18	13.74
Master's Level	151	47.63	39	29.77
Master's Degree	51	16.09	32	24.43
Doctor's Level	8	2.52	26	19.85
Doctor's Degree	2	0.63	16	12.21
Total	317	100.00	131	100.00

Table 2 presents the educational attainment of Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates and School Heads. Nearly half (47.63%) of the Homeroom Guidance Teachers are currently pursuing their Master's degrees, while 33.12% hold only a Bachelor's degree and 16.09% have completed their Master's. Doctoral qualifications remain minimal at 3.15%. This reflects ongoing national efforts to raise educational standards through teacher professional development, as highlighted by Gumaran and Gumarang (2021), and to align with ASEAN regional benchmarks.

In contrast, School Heads show higher academic attainment, with 29.77% pursuing Master's degrees, 24.43% holding Master's degrees, and 32.06% either holding

or pursuing a Doctorate. This is largely driven by policy reforms like K–12 that require stronger leadership credentials. As noted by Tansiongco and Ibarra (2020), school leaders with higher degrees are better equipped to manage reforms. The competitive nature of leadership roles further compels educators to pursue advanced degrees, supported by studies (Aquino et al., 2021; Genizera et al., 2022) linking such qualifications with effective leadership and improved school outcomes.

Teaching Loads of the Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Teaching Loads

Teaching Loads (Hours per week)	Frequency	Percentage
33.50 and Above	13	4.10
31.00 - 33.49	8	2.52
29.50 - 30.99	149	47.00
23.25 - 29.49	51	16.09
17.83 - 23.24	17	5.36
17.82 and below	79	24.92
Total	317	100.00

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of teaching loads among Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates.

The data reveals that nearly half of the respondents (47.00%) handle a teaching load between 29.5 to 30.99 hours per week, while 24.92% have a lighter load of 13.92 to 17.832 hours. A smaller percentage (4.10%) carry the heaviest workload of 33.5 hours and above. These findings highlight significant variations in teaching assignments among guidance professionals in Philippine schools.

The predominance of teachers with 29.50 - 30.99 hour workloads align with the typical teaching loads in Philippine public schools. The prescribed teaching hours in the Philippines are six hours of actual classroom teaching per day for public school teachers, as mandated by Republic Act 4670, also known as the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers. According to DepEd Order No. 5, s. 2024, teachers are required to render eight hours of work per day (or 40 hours in one week), with the remaining two hours allocated for teacher ancillary tasks such as curriculum planning, delivery, and assessment.

According to the Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM, 2023), the Department of Education (DepEd) has been systematically deploying Administrative Officer (AO) II personnel since 2020, reaching a total of 24,519 by 2024. This initiative ensures a 1:1 ratio, with one AO assigned to each school. These officers play a vital role in managing school operations, including record keeping, clerical tasks, and other administrative functions—thereby easing the administrative workload of teachers and allowing them to focus more on instruction.

Highest Level of Seminar/Training Attended on Homeroom Guidance

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates and School Heads in terms of Highest Level of Seminar/Training Attended on Homeroom Guidance

Seminar/Training Attended on Homeroom Guidance	Frequency	Percentage
School	106	23.66
District	113	25.22
Division	94	20.98
Regional	56	12.50
National	50	11.16
International	29	6.47
Total	448	100.00

Table 4 shows that most respondents attended Homeroom Guidance seminars or trainings at the school (23.66%) and district (25.22%) levels, with fewer participating in division (20.98%), regional (12.50%), national (11.16%), and international (6.47%) events. This trend reflects a pyramid-like structure of training accessibility, where opportunities diminish as the scope expands.

Localized trainings, particularly at the school and district levels, are more accessible and frequent. According to Roslindawati et al. (2024), these localized sessions foster collaborative learning and directly address classroom needs, enhancing teachers' pedagogical practices. However, broader-level trainings face logistical challenges such as travel, lodging, and costs—issues that Syafira and Lubis (2023) note are especially burdensome for teachers in remote areas, limiting their access to higher-tier training opportunities.

Position of the Teachers

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates in Terms of Teaching Position

Position	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates		School Heads	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Principal III	0	0.00	1	0.76
Principal II	0	0.00	27	20.61
Principal I	0	0.00	31	23.66
Head Teacher III	0	0.00	28	21.37
Head Teacher II	0	0.00	1	0.76
Head Teacher I	0	0.00	13	9.92

Master Teacher II	10	3.15	1	0.76
Master Teacher I	26	8.20	2	1.53
Teacher III	190	59.94	27	20.61
Teacher II	15	4.73	0	0.00
Teacher I	76	23.98	0	0.00
Total	317	100.00	131	100.00

Table 5 shows that most Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates hold the rank of Teacher III (59.94%), followed by Teacher I (23.98%) and Master Teacher I (8.20%). Meanwhile, School Heads primarily hold administrative positions such as Principal I (23.66%), Head Teacher III (21.37%), and Principal II (20.61%), with few in lower teaching ranks.

In the Philippine context, teachers assigned as homeroom advisers typically hold Teacher III positions due to their professional experience, training, and competency in managing student learning (Gepila, 2020). Teacher III is often granted to educators with at least three years of teaching experience, ensuring they are well-equipped for homeroom responsibilities.

Conversely, school heads involved in homeroom guidance—mostly Principals and Head Teachers—are appointed based on their extensive qualifications and leadership experience. These roles often require a Master’s degree, equipping them with both pedagogical and administrative expertise needed to effectively oversee guidance programs (Antigo & Guzman, 2024). As Tan (2018) highlights, Head Teachers III and above play key roles in managing dynamic and responsive student guidance initiatives, underscoring the leadership function in homeroom program success.

Length of Service of Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates and School Heads

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates		School Heads	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
36 years and above	7	2.21	7	5.34
31 - 35 years	13	4.10	4	3.05
26 - 30 years	17	5.36	14	10.69
21 - 25 years	29	9.15	10	7.63
16 - 20 years	28	8.83	20	15.27
11 - 15 years	48	15.14	12	9.16
6 - 10 years	58	18.30	29	22.14
1 - 5 years	117	36.91	35	26.72
Total	317	100.00	131	100.00

Table 6 presents the distribution of respondents in terms of length of service among Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates and School Heads. The data reveals that the majority of both groups fall within the early to mid-career stages, with 36.91% of Homeroom Guidance Teachers and 26.72% of School Heads having 1-5 years of experience. The distribution shows a gradual decline in numbers as years of service increase, with only 2.21% of guidance teachers and 5.34% of school heads serving for 36 years or more. Notably, School Heads tend to have more representation in the 6-30 years range compared to guidance teachers, particularly in the 16-20 years (15.27%) and 26-30 years (10.69%) brackets.

What is the Extent of Implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela as assessed by the Respondents?

Curriculum Implementation and Compliance

Table 7
Assessment of Respondents on the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program in the Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela with respect to Curriculum Implementation and Compliance

Indicators	Homeroom Guidance Teachers Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. The MELC of the Homeroom Guidance is followed properly	2.72	Fully Implemented	2.75	Fully Implemented	2.74	Fully Implemented	2.73	Fully Implemented
2. The objectives of the program are achieved at the end of the school year	2.65	Fully Implemented	2.68	Fully Implemented	2.69	Fully Implemented	2.67	Fully Implemented
3. The learners' output is regularly monitored	2.61	Fully Implemented	2.69	Fully Implemented	2.66	Fully Implemented	2.64	Fully Implemented
4. Regular meetings of Guidance Counselor/designate with the learners show a positive impact on the learners	2.46	Fully Implemented	2.51	Fully Implemented	2.53	Fully Implemented	2.49	Fully Implemented
5. Learners and parents are acquainted with the competencies that they need to master per domain in each quarter	2.54	Fully Implemented	2.51	Fully Implemented	2.59	Fully Implemented	2.54	Fully Implemented
6. The school is	2.73	Fully	2.82	Fully	2.76	Fully	2.75	Fully

conducting the remote enrolment and considers the inclusivity of all types of learners		Implemented		Implemented		Implemented		Implemented
7. Books and Instructional Materials are contextualized and localized based on the Homeroom Guidance Program	2.40	Fully Implemented	2.41	Fully Implemented	2.53	Fully Implemented	2.44	Fully Implemented
8. Remediation, Enrichment, and Enhancement activities of the Homeroom Guidance Program are conducted through home visitation following IATF Protocols	2.57	Fully Implemented	2.58	Fully Implemented	2.62	Fully Implemented	2.58	Fully Implemented
9. Intervention Program or activities related to HGP Literacy and Numeracy is observed	2.45	Fully Implemented	2.53	Fully Implemented	2.62	Fully Implemented	2.51	Fully Implemented
10. Classroom observation on the HGP Instruction is conducted and School Heads give Technical Assistance if necessary	2.49	Fully Implemented	2.53	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.53	Fully Implemented
Overall Mean	2.56	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.59	Fully Implemented

Table 7 provides an evaluation of the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP) implementation in Legislative District 1, Division of Isabela, based on responses from Homeroom Guidance Teachers/Designates, School Heads, and Parents. All three stakeholder groups consistently rated the program as "Fully Implemented" across all ten indicators, with overall mean scores ranging from 2.51 to 2.63, indicating a strong and successful implementation. Parents rated the program slightly higher (2.63) than teachers (2.56) and school heads (2.60), reflecting a shared positive perception.

The highest-rated indicator across all groups was Indicator 6, which measures the program's inclusivity and adaptability during remote enrollment. This suggests that the district has effectively upheld DepEd's Inclusive Education Framework (DepEd Order No. 43, s. 2013), particularly in response to the shift to distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, when DepEd implemented remote enrollment (DepEd, 2020).

Conversely, Indicator 7, which evaluates the contextualization and localization of instructional materials, received the lowest mean scores, indicating room for improvement. This reflects ongoing challenges related to the Philippines' diverse cultural and linguistic contexts, which complicate efforts to create universally effective educational content. Logistical difficulties and limited collaboration between teachers, local governments, and communities further hinder the development of culturally relevant materials (Cabural, 2024; Navarro & McKinnon, 2020; Colminar & Padullo, 2023). Continued support is needed to help teachers contextualize the HGP curriculum more effectively.

Delivery Process

Table 8
Assessment of Respondents on the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program in the Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela with respect to Delivery Process

Indicators	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Homeroom Guidance classes are programmed for the whole school year	2.73	Fully Implemented	2.79	Fully Implemented	2.76	Fully Implemented	2.75	Fully Implemented
2. Learners and parents are acquainted with the competencies that learners need to master per domain in each quarter	2.53	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.61	Fully Implemented	2.56	Fully Implemented
3. The Class Program reflects teacher's loading and teaching assignments on the Homeroom Guidance program	2.72	Fully Implemented	2.78	Fully Implemented	2.72	Fully Implemented	2.73	Fully Implemented
4. Parents are informed about the competencies to be learned in	2.62	Fully Implemented	2.64	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented

the Homeroom Guidance Program								
Modular Distance learning	2.73	Fully Implemented	2.77	Fully Implemented	2.76	Fully Implemented	2.74	Fully Implemented
Modular Print/Digital	2.87	Fully Implemented	2.93	Fully Implemented	2.81	Fully Implemented	2.86	Fully Implemented
TV -Print	2.75	Fully Implemented	2.73	Fully Implemented	2.73	Fully Implemented	2.75	Fully Implemented
RBI-Print	2.72	Fully Implemented	2.50	Fully Implemented	2.56	Fully Implemented	2.66	Fully Implemented
Overall Mean	2.68	Fully Implemented	2.72	Fully Implemented	2.69	Fully Implemented	2.69	Fully Implemented

Table 8 presents the assessment of respondents on the extent of implementation of HGP in the Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela with respect to delivery process.

The findings reveal that the Homeroom Guidance Program is consistently rated as "Fully Implemented" across all indicators and stakeholder groups. The uniformity in ratings across stakeholders highlights a shared perception of successful implementation, with parents and teachers closely aligned in their assessments. The highest-rated indicator is "Modular Print/Digital" (mean = 2.86), suggesting strong implementation of this learning modality. Conversely, the lowest-rated indicator is "RBI-Print" (mean = 2.66), though it still falls under the "Fully Implemented" category. This indicates that while the program is effectively delivered overall, there may be slight variations in the execution of specific components.

Evaluation of Learners Development

Table 9
Assessment of Respondents on the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program with respect to Assessment of Learners' Development

Indicators	Homeroom Guidance Teachers Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Learners are oriented on the learning objective and how their development will be assessed	2.57	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.59	Fully Implemented
2. Assessment results are explained to the learners, leading to their realization of the	2.55	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.59	Fully Implemented	2.57	Fully Implemented

areas for improvement								
3. Learners can keep track of their progress in the program	2.56	Fully Implemented	2.62	Fully Implemented	2.57	Fully Implemented	2.57	Fully Implemented
4. Documentation of conference with the learners about their development	2.44	Fully Implemented	2.59	Fully Implemented	2.50	Fully Implemented	2.49	Fully Implemented
5. Learner's Development Assessment with remarks of adviser and parent	2.62	Fully Implemented	2.70	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.64	Fully Implemented
6. Teachers assess learnings through the following:								
a. Formative test	2.64	Fully Implemented	2.76	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.66	Fully Implemented
b. Summative Test,	2.72	Fully Implemented	2.81	Fully Implemented	2.66	Fully Implemented	2.73	Fully Implemented
c. Performance-based/Skilled-based Assessment,	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.76	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.64	Fully Implemented
d. Portfolio Assessment	2.59	Fully Implemented	2.70	Fully Implemented	2.57	Fully Implemented	2.61	Fully Implemented
e. Learners respond to the personal and social needs that can contribute to the promotion of community standards	2.50	Fully Implemented	2.49	Fully Implemented	2.47	Fully Implemented	2.49	Fully Implemented
f. Learners strengthen self-empowerment to respond to the needs of the community	2.49	Fully Implemented	2.50	Fully Implemented	2.47	Fully Implemented	2.49	Fully Implemented
g. Learners strengthen the connection among knowledge, skills, and roles of parents or guardians and significant adults in choosing a profession, vocation, and	2.52	Fully Implemented	2.51	Fully Implemented	2.52	Fully Implemented	2.52	Fully Implemented

future plans								
9. Learners apply lessons from home, school, and community to daily living with consideration to family and society	2.58	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.58	Fully Implemented	2.59	Fully Implemented
Overall Mean	2.57	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.58	Fully Implemented

Table 9 presents the assessment of respondents on the extent of implementation of HGP with respect to assessment of learners' development. The findings reveal that the assessment process is consistently rated as "Fully Implemented" across all indicators. The highest-rated aspects include summative assessments (mean = 2.73) and formative tests (mean = 2.66), indicating strong adherence to structured evaluation practices. These quantitative findings are further supported by qualitative data from focus group discussions. Participants reported that teachers primarily assess learners through skills-based and performance-based assessments, utilizing both summative and formative tests as inventory measures to evaluate skills within the rating period. Teachers emphasized the importance of incorporating higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) questions in their assessments, with one participant remarking, *"Madali lang subukin ang kakayahan ng mga mag-aaral kung talagang nag-aaral sila nang mabuti. Dapat laging magpasagot ang teacher ng HOTS questions para subukin ang kanilang talino o husay."* This statement highlights how learners find assessments more meaningful when connected to real-life experiences.

However, slightly lower ratings were given in documentation of conferences about learner development, responsiveness to personal and social needs, and self-empowerment in addressing community needs (all mean = 2.49). Documentation is essential in evaluating cognitive, emotional, and social growth and informs instructional strategies (Irawahyuni et al., 2021). Moreover, Chan et al. (2017) emphasized that service-learning strengthens students' community connection, while García-Toledano et al. (2023) stressed its role in social responsibility. The overall mean of 2.59 confirms that the HGP effectively monitors development, with room for improvement in documentation and formative feedback.

Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation

Table 10
Assessment of Respondents on the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program with Respect to Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation

Indicators	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. A clear	2.60	Fully	2.64	Fully	2.63	Fully	2.61	Fully

Monitoring Plan (Guidance Counselor/ Designate and School Head) before the start of the program is evident		Implemented		Implemented		Implemented		Implemented
2. Monitoring Plan is properly implemented	2.59	Fully Implemented	2.61	Fully Implemented	2.65	Fully Implemented	2.61	Fully Implemented
3. Monitoring results are discussed with the concerned personnel to encourage actions needed to improve the program delivery	2.54	Fully Implemented	2.58	Fully Implemented	2.58	Fully Implemented	2.56	Fully Implemented
4. Monitoring results are utilized to improve the program delivery	2.57	Fully Implemented	2.62	Fully Implemented	2.56	Fully Implemented	2.58	Fully Implemented
5. Proper coordination, planning, and corrective feedback system are being enforced	2.58	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.55	Fully Implemented	2.58	Fully Implemented
6. Considers Homeroom Guidance Program in the Programs, Projects, and Activities of the school	2.61	Fully Implemented	2.73	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.64	Fully Implemented
7. HGP is included in the SIP, AIP, WFP, SBM, and all other Plans of the school	2.66	Fully Implemented	2.75	Fully Implemented	2.64	Fully Implemented	2.68	Fully Implemented
8. School heads, Teachers, Parents, and	2.68	Fully Implemented	2.74	Fully Implemented	2.66	Fully Implemented	2.69	Fully Implemented

learners are oriented as to the HGP								
9. Homeroom Guidance Program is evaluated following the necessary standards	2.67	Fully Implemented	2.67	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.66	Fully Implemented
Overall Mean	2.61	Fully Implemented	2.66	Fully Implemented	2.62	Fully Implemented	2.62	Fully Implemented

Table 10 presents the assessment of respondents on the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP) with respect to supervision. The results indicate strong implementation, with composite mean scores ranging from 2.61 (Teachers/Designates) to 2.66 (School Heads), and an overall composite mean of 2.62. School Heads gave consistently higher ratings, particularly in the inclusion of HGP in school planning documents (mean = 2.75) and stakeholder orientation (mean = 2.74), reflecting strong administrative support. Focus group discussions affirmed this, with participants stating that school heads strictly monitor HGP implementation as part of the School Improvement Plan and School-Based Management. One participant noted, *"Na-realize namin na ang objective pala nito ay para sa ikabubuti ng mga bata, para mahasa ang mga skills nila."*

All respondent groups agreed that the program follows a clear monitoring plan (mean = 2.61) and that results are used to enhance delivery (mean = 2.58). However, challenges were also reported. Some teachers initially underestimated the workload, saying, *"Hindi lang pala ganun kadali ang trabaho ng HGP."* Participants further remarked, *"Mas mabigat pala ang workload ng HG teachers kaysa sa ibang subjects... Kaya pala striktong chine-check palagi ng aming principal ang ginagawa ng mga Homeroom Guidance teachers sa aming school at dito namin napatunayan na very supportive sila bilang administrador sa mga Homeroom Guidance program."*

The lowest mean (2.56) was observed in Indicator 3, concerning discussion of monitoring results with personnel, suggesting a need for stronger feedback mechanisms. Despite this, the consistently high ratings across Indicators 6–9 highlight successful integration of HGP into school planning, confirming effective supervision with room for enhanced collaboration.

Administrative Concerns

Table 11
Assessment of Respondents on the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program with respect to Administrative Concerns

Indicators	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Orientation for learners and their parents is conducted by the school before the start of the School Year.	2.62	Fully Implemented	2.66	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented
2. An adequate budget is allotted for HG expenses.	2.34	Partially Implemented	2.33	Partially Implemented	2.44	Fully Implemented	2.36	Fully Implemented
3. Materials and relevant supplies (online or printed learning materials) are available for the learners and teachers of HG	2.58	Fully Implemented	2.61	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented
4. The learning modality is appropriate and conducive to the conduct of the program	2.58	Fully Implemented	2.65	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented
5. Issues and concerns based on the reports are acted upon or addressed	2.53	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.53	Fully Implemented	2.55	Fully Implemented
6. There is an existing Homeroom Guidance Program, Licensed Homeroom Guidance Coordinator, Homeroom	2.38	Fully Implemented	2.32	Partially Implemented	2.48	Fully Implemented	2.39	Fully Implemented

Guidance Room or corner in the school								
Overall Mean	2.50	Fully Implemented	2.53	Fully Implemented	2.55	Fully Implemented	2.52	Fully Implemented

Table 11 presents the assessment of the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP) in Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela with respect to administrative concerns. Overall, the program is deemed *Fully Implemented* (overall mean = 2.52). High ratings were given to aspects such as orientation for learners and parents before the school year (mean = 2.63), availability of learning materials (mean = 2.60), appropriateness of learning modality (mean = 2.60), and responsiveness to reported concerns (mean = 2.55). However, both Homeroom Guidance teachers/designates and school heads rated the adequacy of the HG budget as *Partially Implemented* (means = 2.34 and 2.33), and school heads gave similar ratings to indicators such as the presence of a licensed HG coordinator, a formal HG program, and a dedicated HG space (mean = 2.32).

Participants in the Focus Group Discussion emphasized administrative support. One noted, *“Kaya pala ganoon na lamang kahalaga ang Homeroom Guidance Program dahil panay panay ang pa-meeting ng school heads namin.”* Others shared, *“Dahil sa programa ng Homeroom Guidance, ang aming principal ay napaka supportive... nagbahagi din ng mga school supplies para sa implementasyon ng programa.”* Some admitted initial skepticism but later recognized its importance: *“Na-realize namin na ang objective pala nito ay para sa ikabubuti ng mga bata.”* Teachers acknowledged the heavy workload, stating, *“Mas mabigat pala ang workload ng HG teachers kaysa magturo ng ibang subjects.”* One participant concluded, *“Kaya pala striktong chine-check palagi ng aming principal... dito namin napatunayan na malaki ang kanilang malasakit.”*

These accounts confirm that administrative efforts have driven the program’s successful implementation despite some logistical challenges.

Summary Assessment of the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program

Table 12
Summary Assessment of the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program in the Division of Isabela

Variables on HG Program	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	2.56	Fully Implemented	2.6	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.59	Fully Implemented
Delivery Process	2.68	Fully Implemented	2.72	Fully Implemented	2.69	Fully Implemented	2.69	Fully Implemented
Assessment of	2.57	Fully	2.63	Fully	2.6	Fully	2.58	Fully

Learners Development		Implemented		Implemented		Implemented		Implemented
Supervision of HG Implementation	2.61	Fully Implemented	2.66	Fully Implemented	2.62	Fully Implemented	2.62	Fully Implemented
Administrative Concerns	2.5	Fully Implemented	2.53	Fully Implemented	2.55	Fully Implemented	2.52	Fully Implemented
Overall Mean	2.58	Fully Implemented	2.63	Fully Implemented	2.61	Fully Implemented	2.60	Fully Implemented

Table 12 presents the summary assessment of the HGP implementation, evaluating five key program components.

The data reveals consistently strong implementation across all program aspects, with all variables rated as "Fully Implemented" (overall mean = 2.60). School Heads consistently provided the highest ratings (mean = 2.63), followed closely by Parents (mean = 2.61) and Teachers/Designates (mean = 2.58). The Delivery Process emerged as the strongest component (mean = 2.69), suggesting particularly effective execution of program activities and teaching methodologies. Administrative Concerns received the lowest ratings among the variables (mean = 2.52), though still within the "Fully Implemented" range, indicating this area may benefit from additional attention despite meeting implementation standards.

Notably, all stakeholder groups showed remarkable alignment in their assessments, with mean scores varying by only 0.05-0.08 points across most variables. This consistency suggests shared recognition of the program's successful implementation. The data particularly highlights School Heads' slightly more positive perceptions, potentially reflecting their leadership perspective on program management and oversight.

These findings demonstrate that the HGP has been effectively institutionalized across the first legislative district of Division of Isabela, with all critical components - from curriculum delivery to learner assessment and program supervision - operating at full implementation levels. The minor variations between component scores provide insights for continuous improvement, particularly in strengthening administrative support systems to match the excellence demonstrated in program delivery and supervision.

Is there a significant difference in the assessment of school heads, Homeroom Guidance Program teachers/designates, school heads, and district Parents on the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program?

3.1. Test of Difference in the assessment of School Heads, HG Program Teachers/Designates, and Parents on the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program

Table 13
Results of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program

Variables	P-value	Analysis	Decision	Interpretation
Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	0.215	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Delivery Process	0.576	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Assessment of Learners Development	0.323	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation	0.574	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Concerns	0.543	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Overall	0.378	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

As shown in Table 13, the results of significant differences in the assessment of School Heads, Homeroom Guidance Program teachers/designates, and parents on the extent of implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program of the Legislative District 1 in the Division of Isabela showed no significant difference in the assessment of school heads, hg program teachers/designates, and parents on the extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program along Curriculum Implementation and Compliance, Delivery Process, Assessment of Learners Development, Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation, and Administrative Concerns a revealed by their p-values with 0.215, 0.576, 0.323, 0.574, and 0.543 as compared with the level of significance which is more than 0.05 indicating the Accept Hypotheses.

Thus, findings could mean that there are no significant differences exist between the assessment of the school heads, homeroom guidance program teachers/designates, and parents on the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program. This implies that regardless of who the implementers are in the Homeroom Guidance Program, the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program has the same implementation whether the implementer is a School Head, HG Program teacher/designate, or PTA officer for that matter, meaning, the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program is the same.

Is there a significant relationship between the respondent's profile and their assessment of the Extent of Implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Division of Isabela?

Highest Educational Attainment

Table 14
Results of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Assessment of the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program and their Highest Educational Attainment

Variables	P – value	Analysis	Decision	Interpretation
Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	0.499	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Delivery Process	0.444	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Assessment of Learners' Development	0.402	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation	0.117	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Concerns	0.905	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Overall	0.950	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

As indicated in Table 14, results of the test of relationship between the respondents' assessment of the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program of the Legislative District 1 in the Division of Isabela and their highest educational attainment the significance of χ^2 or P-values which are more than 0.05 implies that the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 significance level as shown by the p-value with 0.499, 0.444, 0.402, 0.117, and 0.905, respectively. This means that the respondents' assessment on the extent of implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program in terms of curriculum implementation and compliance, delivery process, assessment of learners' development, supervision of homeroom guidance implementation, and administrative concerns is not significantly related to their highest educational attainment.

Generally, the overall significance of χ^2 or P-value of 0.950, which is more than 0.05 indicating acceptance of the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance implying the respondents' assessment of the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program which is not related to their educational attainment.

This concludes that respondents' educational attainment is not an indicator of determining the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program of the Legislative District 1 in the Division of Isabela. Contrary, there is a significant relationship between the highest educational attainment and the extent of implementation of homeroom guidance programs along academic development as indicated by a significance value of .000, which is less than the set level of significance, which is .05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result of this study is parallel to the study of Hoffman (2014), which found that level of education affects the teachers' willingness to help students focus on academic matters.

Teaching Load

Table 15
Results of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Assessment of the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program and their Workload

Variables	P – value	Analysis	Decision	Interpretation
Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	0.253	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Delivery Process	0.315	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Assessment of Learners' Development	0.428	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation	0.172	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Concerns	0.089	P<0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Overall	0.462	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

In Table 15, the results of the test on the relationship between the respondents' assessment of the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela and their teaching load show that all significance values (χ^2 or p-values) exceed 0.05. Specifically, the p-values are 0.253, 0.315, 0.428, 0.172, and 0.089, respectively. These values indicate that the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the respondents' assessment—aligned with the findings of Volante (2022)—of the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in terms of curriculum implementation and compliance, delivery process, assessment of learners' development, supervision of program implementation, and administrative concerns is not significantly related to their teaching load. This suggests that designated Homeroom Guidance teachers, regardless of whether they have heavier or lighter teaching loads, demonstrate a comparable level of program implementation.

Seminar/Training Attended on Homeroom Guidance

Table 16
Results of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Assessment on the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program and their Seminar/Training Attended on Homeroom Guidance

Variables	P – value	Analysis	Decision	Interpretation
Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	0.142	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Delivery Process	0.039	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Assessment of Learners' Development	0.100	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Supervision of Homeroom	0.181	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Guidance Implementation				
Administrative Concerns	0.308	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Overall	0.248	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 16 presents the results of the test of relationship between respondents' assessment of the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP) in Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela and their participation in seminars or training related to homeroom guidance. The significance levels (p-values = 0.142, 0.100, 0.181, and 0.308) for curriculum implementation and compliance, assessment of learners' development, supervision of implementation, and administrative concerns are all above 0.05. This means there is no significant relationship between respondents' assessments in these areas and their highest educational attainment; the null hypothesis is accepted at the 0.05 level of significance.

However, a different result was observed in the area of program delivery. The test of relationship for the delivery process yielded a p-value of 0.039, which is below the 0.05 threshold, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests a significant relationship between seminar/training attendance and better delivery of the HGP. Specifically, designated Homeroom Guidance teachers who attended related training were found to perform better in program delivery. This result may be attributed to a deeper understanding of their roles and responsibilities gained through professional development.

The finding highlights the importance of training and aligns with Joho et al. (2024), who emphasized that training enhances teachers' competence in guiding students, particularly in making informed decisions about their future education and career paths. Districts that prioritize teacher development may achieve more effective HGP implementation than those that do not.

Position

Table 17

Results of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Assessment on the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program and their Position

Variables	P – value	Analysis	Decision	Interpretation
Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	0.469	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Delivery Process	0.708	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Assessment of Learners' Development	0.859	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation	0.498	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Concerns	0.994	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Overall	0.963	P>0.05	Accept	Not Significant

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As reflected in Table 17, data on the results of test of relationship between the respondents' assessment on the extent of implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program of the Legislative District 1 in the Division of Isabela when related to their position, the significance of χ^2 or P-values which are more than 0.05 implies that the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 significance level as shown by the p-value with 0.469, 0.708, 0.859, 0.048 and 0.994, respectively.

This means that the respondents' assessment on the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program, in terms of curriculum implementation and compliance, assessment of learners' development, and supervision of homeroom guidance implementation, and administrative concerns is not significantly related to their position.

Finding implies that regardless of the respondents' position, their assessment on the extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance remains the same.

Length of Service as Teacher of School Head

Table 18

Results of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Assessment of the Extent of Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program and their Length of Service as Teacher or School Head

Variables	P – value	Analysis	Decision	Interpretation
Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	0.829	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Delivery Process	0.450	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Assessment of Learners' Development	0.377	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation	0.108	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Administrative Concerns	0.077	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Overall	0.083	P<0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

As shown in Table 18, data on the results of the test of relationship between the respondents' assessment of the extent of implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program of the Legislative District 1 in the Division of Isabela when related to their Length of Service, the significance of χ^2 or P-values which are more than 0.05 implies that the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 significance level as shown by the p-value with 0.829, 0.450, 0.377, 0.108 and 0.077, respectively.

This means that regardless of the length of service spent by the respondents, their assessment on the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program, relative to curriculum implementation and compliance, assessment of learners' development, and supervision of homeroom guidance implementation, and administrative concerns are with the same assessment with their counterpart.

What are the challenges/problems encountered by the designated Homeroom Guidance Counselor (Teachers) during the Implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela?

Curriculum Implementation and Compliance

Table 19
Challenges Encountered along the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program with respect to Curriculum Implementation and Compliance

Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Congruence of MELC to the Homeroom Guidance and its implementation	1.41	Not a Problem	1.44	Not a Problem	1.49	Not a Problem	1.43	Not a Problem
2. Adequacy of Instructional Materials for the HGP	1.50	Not a Problem	1.60	Not a Problem	1.63	Not a Problem	1.55	Not a Problem
3. Availability of time to monitor learners' output despite printing of Modules	1.64	Not a Problem	1.63	Not a Problem	1.58	Not a Problem	1.63	Not a Problem
4. Sufficiency of the meeting of the Guidance Counselor/designate with the learners	1.56	Not a Problem	1.65	Not a Problem	1.56	Not a Problem	1.58	Not a Problem
5. Learners and parents' familiarity with the competencies that they need to master per domain in each quarter	1.62	Not a Problem	1.69	Serious Problem	1.62	Not a Problem	1.63	Not a Problem
6. Conduct of remote enrolment and consideration of the inclusivity of all types of learners	1.51	Not a Problem	1.56	Not a Problem	1.54	Not a Problem	1.53	Not a Problem
7. Conduct	1.52	Not a	1.58	Not a	1.56	Not a	1.55	Not a

remediation, enrichment, and enhancement activities of the Program		Problem		Problem		Problem		Problem
8. Availability of activities related to HGP Literacy and Numeracy	1.57	Not a Problem	1.56	Not a Problem	1.59	Not a Problem	1.57	Not a Problem
9. Sufficiency of time in Classroom observation on the HGP Instruction	1.53	Not a Problem	1.57	Not a Problem	1.53	Not a Problem	1.54	Not a Problem
Overall Mean	1.53	Not a Problem	1.59	Not a Problem	1.57	Not a Problem	1.55	Not a Problem

Table 19 presents the assessment of challenges encountered in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP) in terms of curriculum implementation and compliance. Overall, the program is successfully implemented, with a general rating of “Not a Problem” (mean = 1.55) across nine indicators. Strong alignment between the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) and the HGP was observed (Indicator 1, mean = 1.43). However, Indicators 3 and 5 posed the most significant challenges.

Indicator 3, “Availability of Time to Monitor Learners' Output” (mean = 1.63), revealed systemic time constraints, especially for teachers (mean = 1.64) and school heads (mean = 1.68). Teachers cited that monitoring is often neglected due to other responsibilities: *“Nakakaligtan ng mga guro ang paggabay... kasi masyado nilang pinagtutuunan ng pansin ang paghahanda ng module, mag-distribute ng module, at mag-collect ng module.”* Five participants added, *“Hindi dapat trabaho ng guro ang IM production... naisasakripisyo ang kalidad ng edukasyon.”* One participant concluded, *“Yan din sa aking palagay ang rason kung bakit walang natututunan masyado ang mga bata noong kalakasan ng pandemic...”* These responses reflect the teacher overload during modular learning, as supported by Cabardo et al. (2022).

Indicator 5, “Learners’ and Parents’ Familiarity with Competencies,” also rated highest (mean = 1.69 by school heads), suggesting a disconnect in understanding the program’s learning objectives. This highlights the need for better communication between teachers and parents to ensure shared support for students. Improved parent awareness enhances student well-being and academic outcomes.

Table 20 presents the assessment of the challenges encountered in implementing the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP) with respect to the delivery process. All stakeholder groups—teachers, school heads, and parents—rated all indicators as “Not a Problem,” with an overall mean of 1.48. Programming of HGP classes (Indicator 1, mean = 1.49) and teacher assignments (Indicator 2, mean = 1.47) were particularly well-rated, indicating effective planning and deployment. Implementation of the HGP Teaching Guide (Indicator 3, mean = 1.50) also received favorable scores. The narrow variance among indicators suggests consistently smooth implementation.

Delivery Process

Table 20
Challenges Encountered along the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program with respect to the Delivery Process

Delivery Process	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Programming of Homeroom Guidance classes for the whole school year	1.48	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem	1.53	Not a Problem	1.49	Not a Problem
2. Implementation of the Class Program by teachers and their teaching assignment on the Homeroom Guidance program	1.45	Not a Problem	1.46	Not a Problem	1.50	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem
3. Teachers' implementation of the HGP Teaching Guide	1.51	Not a Problem	1.49	Not a Problem	1.50	Not a Problem	1.50	Not a Problem
Overall Mean	1.47	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem	1.51	Not a Problem	1.48	Not a Problem

However, qualitative data revealed contrasting insights. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) exposed significant challenges during the pandemic, especially with modular learning. Teachers shared: *“Noong pandemic crisis, ang hirap talagang isagawa ang Homeroom Guidance Program implementation sa kadahilanang ang Distance Learning ang napiling modality.”* Students, overwhelmed with academic tasks, disengaged from the program: *“Mahirap talagang maisagawa ang Homeroom Guidance Program through modular learning dahil ang mga bata ay napapagod na sa dami ng kanilang Assessment tasks bawat subject.”*

Another key issue was the program's non-graded nature: *“Ang Homeroom Guidance ay walang puntos sa grade ng mga bata kung kaya't ang mga mag-aaral ay hindi nagiging seryoso.”* Teachers also saw HGP as an extra burden: *“Ito ay isang gawain [na] pwede namang gampanan na lamang sana ng parents sa bahay.”*

The contrast between positive survey responses and critical FGD insights suggests that respondents focused on post-pandemic delivery, overlooking earlier implementation challenges. Thus, future efforts should address grading incentives, improve delivery modes, and reduce teacher workload.

Assessment of Learner's Development

Table 21
Challenges Encountered along the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program with regard to Assessment of Learners' Development

Assessment of Learners' Development	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Teachers' use of the traditional way of evaluating learning outcomes	1.41	Not a Problem	1.46	Not a Problem	1.53	Not a Problem	1.45	Not a Problem
2. Teachers' workload	1.56	Not a Problem	1.64	Not a Problem	1.60	Not a Problem	1.59	Not a Problem
3. Clients' cooperation	1.61	Not a Problem	1.60	Not a Problem	1.63	Not a Problem	1.61	Not a Problem
4. Parents' support	1.60	Not a Problem	1.62	Not a Problem	1.64	Not a Problem	1.61	Not a Problem
Overall Mean	1.53	Not a Problem	1.58	Not a Problem	1.60	Not a Problem	1.56	Not a Problem

Table 21 presents the assessment of challenges encountered in assessing learners' development within the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP), based on responses from teachers, school heads, and parents. The findings show that assessment-related challenges are minimal, with an overall mean of 1.56 ("Not a Problem"). Teachers' use of traditional evaluation methods (Indicator 1, mean = 1.45) received the most favorable rating, affirming that such methods remain effective for HGP. As noted by Hu (2018), these culturally rooted practices support holistic learning in guidance settings.

Workload concerns (Indicator 2, mean = 1.59) were slightly higher but still manageable. Interviews revealed deeper insights, with one teacher stating: *"Daig pa ng Homeroom Guidance class ang isang subject na ituro...inaasahan dito ang tulong ng mga magulang at ibang stakeholders kung talagang gustong ma-implement ng DepEd."* Homeroom teachers shoulder multifaceted responsibilities beyond academics, including managing students' emotional and social development, often without adequate time or resources.

Indicators on client cooperation and parent support (both mean = 1.61) also showed low challenge levels but were the highest among indicators. Despite this, participants emphasized parental involvement as vital. A teacher noted worsening student discipline: *"Ngunit, nakalulungkot isipin na ang mga bata ay mahirap disiplinahin... hindi masyado natutugunan ng atensyon ng kanilang mga magulang."*

Parental guidance lays the groundwork for values and discipline, complementing school efforts. As research shows, when parents and schools collaborate, students

benefit from consistent reinforcement of values. Moreover, student involvement fosters ownership and personal growth. As Durfee et al. (2020) affirmed, active participation leads to improved academic performance and higher-order thinking.

Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation

Table 22
Challenges Encountered along the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program with respect to Supervision of HG Implementation

Supervision of HG Implementation	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Adequacy of supervision of administrators	1.47	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem
2. Implementation of Monitoring Plan	1.46	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem	1.50	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem
3. Adequacy of Qualified personnel in the field of HGP	1.57	Not a Problem	1.63	Not a Problem	1.57	Not a Problem	1.58	Not a Problem
4. Support from the administrator	1.41	Not a Problem	1.44	Not a Problem	1.50	Not a Problem	1.44	Not a Problem
5. Inclusion of HGP in the SIP, AIP, WFP, SBM, and all other Plans of the school	1.47	Not a Problem	1.43	Not a Problem	1.50	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem
6. Evaluation of the Homeroom Guidance Program following the necessary standards	1.45	Not a Problem	1.44	Not a Problem	1.50	Not a Problem	1.46	Not a Problem
Overall Mean	1.47	Not a Problem	1.48	Not a Problem	1.51	Not a Problem	1.48	Not a Problem

Table 22 presents the assessment of challenges in supervising the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP), showing generally positive outcomes, with an overall mean of 1.48 ("Not a Problem") across six supervision indicators. This suggests effective administrative support and strong monitoring systems. Indicators such as administrative supervision (mean = 1.47), implementation of monitoring plans (mean = 1.47), and integration into school planning (mean = 1.47) received particularly favorable ratings, confirming consistent oversight. Administrator support (Indicator 4) recorded the most positive result (mean = 1.44), highlighting active school leadership in HGP implementation.

However, the adequacy of qualified personnel (Indicator 3) registered the highest challenge score (mean = 1.58), with school heads expressing the most concern (mean = 1.63). Interviews revealed two key issues: the lack of district-level guidance experts and

overburdened teachers handling multiple roles. One participant stated: *“Totoong may mga nag-undergo ng training sa Homeroom Guidance Program, ngunit hindi sapat ang kanilang natutunan dahil sa limitadong oras ng kanilang pagkatuto.”* Another emphasized the struggle of multi-tasking teachers: *“Talagang hati ang kanilang oras sa kanilang mga trabaho sa school kasama ang HGP.”*

Stakeholders unanimously agreed on the need for specialized guidance personnel, as one noted: *“Iba lang talaga ang full-time Guidance Counselor na mag-handle... Kasi equipped sila sa skills ng Guidance.”* Calls to *“Maghire sana ang DepEd ng mga talagang experts sa Homeroom Guidance Program”* reinforce this. Research supports assigning qualified counselors, especially during crises, to ensure ethical, effective guidance. It is recommended that DepEd either hire full-time counselors or comprehensively train teachers to meet guidance standards.

Administrative Concerns

Table 23
Challenges Encountered along the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program with respect to Administrative Concerns

Administrative Concerns	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Adequacy of facilities	1.68	Serious Problem	1.76	Serious Problem	1.65	Not a Problem	1.69	Serious Problem
2. Sufficiency of budget allotted for HG expenses	1.72	Serious Problem	1.71	Serious Problem	1.67	Serious Problem	1.71	Serious Problem
3. Adequacy of Instructional Materials	1.63	Not a Problem	1.61	Not a Problem	1.61	Not a Problem	1.62	Not a Problem
4. Appropriateness and conduciveness of learning modality	1.57	Not a Problem	1.56	Not a Problem	1.52	Not a Problem	1.56	Not a Problem
5. Action taken on issues and concerns reported	1.55	Not a Problem	1.53	Not a Problem	1.50	Not a Problem	1.53	Not a Problem
Overall Mean	1.62	Not a Problem	1.64	Not a Problem	1.59	Not a Problem	1.62	Not a Problem

Table 23 illustrates stakeholder evaluations of administrative challenges in the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP). While most indicators were rated as “Not a Problem,” two critical issues emerged: adequacy of facilities (mean=1.69) and budget sufficiency (mean=1.71). Both were consistently rated as a “Serious Problem,” particularly by educators and school heads, with teachers scoring facility adequacy at 1.68 and school heads at 1.76. Parents also acknowledged the issue but to a slightly lesser extent (mean=1.65). Budget constraints drew universal concern across all groups.

These quantitative findings were echoed in focus group discussions, where stakeholders voiced frustration over limited resources. One participant encapsulated the sentiment: *“Ang programa ng Homeroom Guidance ay may napakagandang hangarin. Subalit nakalulungkot isipin na hindi lahat ay naipro-provide o naibibigay ang pangangailangan ng mga estudyante.”* This statement highlights the gap between the program’s ideal goals and the practical limitations faced during execution.

In contrast, instructional materials (mean=1.62), learning modalities (mean=1.56), and issue resolution (mean=1.53) were positively rated, suggesting that while some aspects of HGP are functioning well, resource infrastructure remains a major hurdle.

These findings align with previous studies. Siyez et al. identified limited time, large class sizes, and lack of training as common barriers, while Achieng (as cited by Boitt, 2016) and Okere (2005) emphasized that administrative shortcomings and financial constraints undermine effective guidance services, especially in resource-poor areas.

To ensure HGP’s success, stakeholders must address these core infrastructure and budgetary issues through deliberate investment and support.

Mean Summary of the Challenges/Problems Encountered by the Respondents along Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program

Table 24
Mean Summary of the Challenges/Problems Encountered along the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program

Administrative Concerns	Homeroom Guidance Teachers/ Designates		School Heads		Parents		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	1.53	Not a Problem	1.59	Not a Problem	1.57	Not a Problem	1.55	Not a Problem
2. Delivery Process	1.47	Not a Problem	1.47	Not a Problem	1.51	Not a Problem	1.48	Not a Problem
3. Assessment of Learner’s Development	1.53	Not a Problem	1.58	Not a Problem	1.60	Not a Problem	1.56	Not a Problem
4. Supervision of Homeroom Guidance Implementation	1.47	Not a Problem	1.48	Not a Problem	1.51	Not a Problem	1.48	Not a Problem
5. Administrative Concerns	1.62	Not a Problem	1.64	Not a Problem	1.59	Not a Problem	1.62	Not a Problem
General Mean	1.52	Not a Problem	1.55	Not a Problem	1.55	Not a Problem	1.54	Not a Problem

Table 24 provides a comprehensive summary of challenges encountered across five key dimensions of the HGP implementation, as reported by teachers, school heads,

and parents. The data reveals generally positive results, with all dimensions rated as "Not a Problem" (General Mean = 1.54).

The findings indicate that program delivery (mean=1.48) and supervision (mean=1.48) are particularly well-implemented, suggesting effective execution of classroom activities and administrative oversight. Assessment practices (mean=1.56) and curriculum compliance (mean=1.55) also show strong performance, reflecting proper adherence to learning standards and evaluation processes.

While administrative concerns received slightly higher challenge scores (mean=1.62), they still fall within the "Not a Problem" range. However, this dimension warrants attention as it represents the area with the most room for improvement. Notably, parents consistently reported marginally higher challenge perceptions across all dimensions (means: 1.51-1.60) compared to educators (means: 1.47-1.64), though these differences are minimal.

The consistently positive ratings across all implementation aspects suggest that the HGP is functioning effectively overall. The minor variations between dimensions indicate that while no major systemic issues exist, administrators could focus on strengthening administrative support systems to further enhance program quality. These results demonstrate successful institutionalization of the HGP, with all critical components operating at satisfactory levels.

Is there a significant relationship between the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program and the challenges encountered?

Table 25
Test of Relationship Between the Implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program and Challenges Encountered

Extent of Implementation	Challenges Encountered Along Homeroom Guidance Program											
	Curriculum Implementation and Compliance		Delivery Process		Assessment of Learners Development		Supervision of HG Implementation		Admin Concerns		Overall	
	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Curriculum Implementation and Compliance	-0.34*	0.00	-0.24*	0.00	-0.29*	0.00	-0.30*	0.00	-0.36*	0.00	-0.33*	0.00
Delivery Process	-0.24*	0.00	-0.19*	0.00	-0.22*	0.00	-0.24*	0.00	-0.26*	0.00	-0.24*	0.00
Assessment of Learners Dev't	-0.28*	0.00	-0.20*	0.00	-0.23*	0.00	-0.26*	0.00	-0.26*	0.00	-0.26*	0.00
Supervision of HG Implementation	-0.25*	0.00	-0.15*	0.00	-0.17*	0.00	-0.24*	0.00	-0.27*	0.00	-0.23*	0.00
Administrative Concerns	-0.27*	0.00	-0.20*	0.00	-0.22*	0.00	-0.24*	0.00	-0.28*	0.00	-0.26*	0.00
Overall	-0.30*	0.00	-0.21*	0.00	-0.24*	0.00	-0.27*	0.00	-0.30*	0.00	-0.28*	0.00

Note: $p < 0.05$

Table 25 reveals a significant inverse relationship between the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP) and the challenges encountered by stakeholders in the Legislative District 1 of the Division of Isabela. A correlation of -0.34 ($p < 0.05$) indicates that as curriculum implementation improves, challenges diminish—particularly in monitoring learners' output. One participant emphasized, "*Mahirap talagang pagsabayin ang magturo at magprinta ng module at the same time,*" suggesting a need for ready-made instructional materials.

Similarly, a -0.19 correlation in the delivery process shows difficulty in implementation due to the absence of teaching guides. A teacher noted, "*Mahirap din kasi magdisenyo ng strategies kung walang Teachers' Guide for Homeroom Guidance na sinusunod.*" This implies that education authorities should prioritize developing teacher guides.

The -0.23 correlation in learner assessment indicates documentation struggles and lack of cooperation from parents and students. "Kakaiba talaga ang ugali ng mga kabataan ngayon... Yung mga parents nila ay inaasa na lang sa teacher," shared one respondent. This highlights the need to involve and educate parents on their supportive role.

Supervision-related issues also revealed a -0.24 correlation, attributed to a lack of qualified personnel. "Iba talaga ang full-time Guidance Counselor... bihasa sila sa skills ng guidance," a participant affirmed, stressing the need for specialized staffing.

Finally, the -0.28 correlation in administrative concerns reflects issues like insufficient budget. One said, "Ang programa... ay may napakagandang hangarin... subalit... hindi ito naibigay ang pangangailangan ng mga estudyante." Strengthening program support, training, and funding is vital to reducing implementation challenges and enhancing student development outcomes.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were arrived at based on the findings of this study.

The assessment of the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Division of Isabela (Legislative District 1) indicates that stakeholders generally view the program as fully implemented across all indicators. This favorable perception can foster increased support for the program and enhance collaboration among all involved parties.

However, improvements may be considered in allotting adequate budget for Homeroom Guidance expenses and ensuring the establishment of key components such as a fully implemented Homeroom Guidance Program, a designated Homeroom Guidance Coordinator, and a dedicated Homeroom Guidance Room.

Meanwhile, the fact that the stakeholders have the same assessment on the implementation of the HGP indicates a strong consensus that can positively influence

collaboration, trust, and engagement among all parties involved. This alignment provides a solid foundation for identifying areas for improvement and advocating for necessary resources.

Additionally, Guidance teachers who participated in seminars and training were more effective than those who did not. This indicates that the sustainability and enhancement program should prioritize training for Guidance teachers of tool subjects and those with limited seminar exposure. By focusing on these areas, schools can improve program delivery and ensure all educators have the skills needed to support student development effectively.

Despite positive indicators, significant challenges persist. The survey revealed significant administrative challenges, primarily related to insufficient budgetary allocations and inadequate facilities and teaching resources. The Homeroom Guidance Program should be included in the School Improvement Plan, Annual Implementation Plan, or Work Implementation Plan. Schools may also create a Homeroom Guidance Corner in each classroom or school and hold orientation sessions for new guidance advocates. These measures will foster a supportive environment for students and staff, ensuring the program is well-integrated into the school's framework.

The negative correlation between HGP implementation and encountered challenges indicates that effective implementation leads to fewer perceived problems. Enhancing program delivery is crucial to reducing obstacles faced by educators and stakeholders. Continued professional development, improved administrative support, and increased parental involvement are essential for creating a supportive environment for students' personal and social development through the guidance program. By focusing on these areas, schools can strengthen the HGP and effectively meet the needs of all students.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby considered to sustain and enhance the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Division of Isabela.

1. The DepEd officials in Legislative District 1 may consider improving the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance program. This may be done through the following:
 - a. allocate an adequate budget to support the Homeroom Guidance program and its activities; and
 - b. hiring of competent Licensed Guidance Counselor may be considered as an urgent need in the basic elementary education;
2. The school administrators may initiate the conduct of regular training workshops and Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions on the strategies of implementing the Homeroom Guidance through Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) to share their best practices, thereby sustaining and enhancing the implementation of Homeroom Guidance Program in their respective schools.

3. Since the Homeroom Guidance (HG) teachers with non-tool subject teaching loads tend to have better implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in terms of administrative concerns, and that HG teachers who have attended seminars and training at various levels tend to implement the program's delivery process more fully, there is a need to:

- a. consider reducing the teaching load of Homeroom Guidance teachers or providing them with additional administrative support to allow them to focus on the effective implementation of the program; and
- b. mandate that all Homeroom Guidance teachers attend seminars and training sessions at the school-based, district-based, and division levels to ensure they have a thorough understanding of the Homeroom Guidance Program and its delivery process.

4. Given that school heads, homeroom guidance designates, and parents have encountered serious problems during the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program, particularly in terms of administrative concerns, assessment of learners' development, and curriculum implementation and compliance, then:

- a. Administrative concerns may be addressed by:
 - i) increasing the budget allocated for Homeroom Guidance expenses to ensure that the program has sufficient resources to be effectively implemented for the needs of the Homeroom Guidance Program to meet the requirements needed facilities for counseling, psychological materials, and other office equipment to enhance a positive environment for guidance and counseling activities;
 - ii) improving the adequacy of facilities used for Homeroom Guidance activities to create a conducive learning environment for students; and
- b. Enhance Assessment of Learners' Development through:
 - i) implementing strategies to improve clients' cooperation and parents' support for the Homeroom Guidance Program, such as conducting awareness campaigns and fostering stronger partnerships with families; and
 - ii) providing training for teachers on alternative assessment methods that go beyond traditional ways of evaluating learning outcomes, such as portfolio assessments, project-based learning, and performance-based assessments.
- c. Strengthen Curriculum Implementation and Compliance by means of:
 - i) exploring ways to free up time for homeroom guidance designates to monitor learners' output, such as reducing their teaching load or providing additional administrative support;
 - ii) developing and implementing strategies to increase learners' and parents' familiarity with the competencies that students need to master per domain in each quarter, such as providing clear and accessible information about the curriculum and its expectations; and
 - iii) ensuring that the Homeroom Guidance Program's curriculum is aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) and that its implementation is consistent with the program's objectives.

5. Given that there is an inverse relationship between the extent of implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program and the challenges encountered by the respondents, the

following are the strategies to sustain the effective implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program:

- a. ensure that the Homeroom Guidance Program continues to be implemented with a high degree of fidelity, as this appears to be a key factor in minimizing the challenges encountered during implementation;
- b. allocate sufficient resources, including funding, facilities, and personnel, to support the continued effective implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program.
- c. offer regular training and professional development opportunities for homeroom guidance teachers and other stakeholders to keep them up-to-date with best practices and to address any emerging challenges.
- d. showcase the program's successes and positive impact on students to build momentum and inspire continued commitment from all stakeholders.

6. Implement an intervention program to sustain and enhance the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in the Division of Isabela.

7. A similar study may be conducted, considering other factors that can affect the implementation of the Homeroom Guidance Program in schools, the result of which could be utilized by future researchers and could serve as a ready reference for their research study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of Isabela for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

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